

Theorising the third space

Stephen Abblitt

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The massive growth of hybrid roles crossing the traditional academic/ professional boundary in higher education has given rise to voluminous research and theory on the so-called “third space”, most notably by Whitchurch (2008, 2012). But what is the third space? What are the conceptual origins of the third space, and what does this mean for our use of the term here and now today, and for our practices and positionalities, individually and collectively, as third space professionals?

This interactive presentation challenged participants to reflect on a critical–philosophical genealogy of the concept through three key twentieth-century thinkers: Jacques Derrida, Homi Bhabha, and Edward Soja.

- Derrida’s (1982) concept of *différance* was theorised as a critical gesture for opening the gap or interval between binarized oppositions such as speech/writing, here/there, self/other, insider/outsider, or academic/professional.
- This informed Bhabha’s (2004) theorisation of the liminal or interstitial “third space” where cultural encounters occurred, and where new identities and possibilities emerged, between dominant and subordinate cultures.
- Soja’s (1996) “third space” then complemented Bhabha’s perspective, exploring how different spatial practices and discourses intersected but also fostered sites of resistance to dominant power structures.

By tracing the genealogy of the concept, the presentation hoped to better inform our understanding of third space roles, identities and positions, as well as how such thought can be harnessed to challenge and transform dominant institutional power structures that seek to marginalise those of us who work in that gap or interval between the academic and the professional.

In the ensuing workshop and discussion, participants were challenged to draw on their collective personal and professional experience working in the “third space” to explore and test how this critical–philosophical genealogy of the concept might inform our understanding of our “third space” roles and identities now and into the future, including the potential challenges or limitations in applying the concept of the “third space” to our work. This included creating/drawing their own spatial metaphors to describe the spaces we inhabit and our interstitial positionality within the university.

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About the author

Stephen Abblitt

Keypath

Stephen Abblitt is a learning designer, educational researcher and literary scholar. He is currently Academic Development Manager for Keypath Education (Asia-Pacific).

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6866-2225>

[Google Scholar](#)

[LinkedIn](#)